

CULTIVATION, HARVEST, PROCESSING, AND MARKETING OF WALNUTS FROM AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS IN GERMANY

1. Walnuts ripening 2. Manual harvesting of walnuts 3. Walnut cracking machine 4. Sorting belt for qualitative selection of walnuts at Walnut Mastery Böllersen. (Photos: Fischer / ZALF).

WHAT AND WHY

Walnut cultivation is gaining recognition as a sustainable, profitable agroforestry practice in Germany. Integrating walnut trees with crops or grassland creates diverse and resilient systems with ecological and economic benefits. Valued for their nutritious nuts and premium timber, walnuts also meet the growing demand for regional and sustainable products. Walnuts' nutritional value - rich in healthy fats, protein, and antioxidants - supports both human health and the development of value-added food products.

Key practices include site-adapted variety selection, careful planting and maintenance, pruning for timber quality, and proper harvesting and processing techniques. Walnut-based agroforestry systems - whether silvoarable, silvopastoral or agrisilvopastoral - enhance biodiversity, soil health, and climate resilience, while supporting rural economies, sustainable food production, and the bioeconomy.

Keywords: Walnut cultivation, Sustainable food production, Timber and nut value, Management, Market opportunities, Ecosystem services

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

With domestic production meeting only a fraction of demand, walnut cultivation in Germany offers significant opportunities, but requires careful site selection, effective management, and patience for long-term returns. Diversifying into value-added products can significantly boost profitability. However, nut quality and reduced losses rely on efficient post-harvest handling. Local cooperatives and advisory networks are vital for technical support, shared processing, and better market access. Integrating walnuts into agroforestry systems further enhances resilience, biodiversity, and soil health, while strengthening rural economies and sustainable food production.

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ADVANTAGES

Walnut cultivation offers diverse, long-term income from nuts, timber, and other valuable by-products. Strong market prospects are driven by growing demand for local and sustainable goods. Walnuts can be processed into nutritious foods such as snacks, oil, tea, liquor, sweeteners, and flour, while their wood is highly valued. This boosts rural employment and local value chains. Ecologically, walnuts improve soil structure, reduce erosion, retain water, sequester carbon, and provide habitats for wildlife. Many varieties are resilient to drought and variable soils, making them adaptable to different regions and farm systems.

DISADVANTAGES

Walnut trees require 7-10 years for significant yields, demanding patience and delaying profits. Success depends on careful site selection. Walnuts are vulnerable to pests (such as walnut husk fly) and diseases (notably bacterial blight), requiring regular monitoring and intervention. Timely harvest, proper drying, and storage are crucial for quality, but small producers may lack efficient processing and marketing infrastructure. Initial investments for planting material, site preparation, and infrastructure are high. Walnuts are also sensitive to late frost, which can affect yield and quality.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Select varieties proven in your region; recommended German types include 'Kurmarker Walnuss', 'Ockerwitzer Lange', 'Seifersdorfer Runde', and Geisenheimer varieties. Foreign options include 'Franquette', 'Lara', 'Fernor', 'Scharsch', 'Broadview', and 'Mars'. Prioritize deep, well-drained soils with good water access. Plant in strips with 12-15 meters spacing for optimal growth and disease prevention. Use manual or mechanical harvesting; clean, dry (to 6-12% moisture), and store nuts properly. Explore regional markets and cooperatives, and plan for long-term sustainability. Integrate walnuts into broader or mixed agroforestry systems to spread risk where possible.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Walnut agroforestry in Germany combines ecological and economic benefits, producing nutritious nuts, valuable timber and other valuable by-products while supporting rural economies, resilience, and multiple ecosystem services.**
- **Successful cultivation requires careful site selection, adapted varieties, effective management, and patience due to long maturation periods and delayed profits.**
- **Walnuts offer strong market potential but face challenges such as high initial investment, pest and disease risks, and the need for efficient harvesting, processing, and marketing infrastructure.**

Walnut as a multifunctional tree species with diverse potential uses
(Photo: Fischer / ZALF)

REFERENCES:

Böllersen, V. (2019). Revival der Walnuss: Neues und altes Wissen zum Walnussanbau in Deutschland. 2nd revised edition. OLV: Kevelaer. EAN: 978-3-922201-95-3

DANIEL FISCHER*

* Leibniz Center for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), working group "Agricultural Economics and Ecosystem Services"

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.